

THE INTRODUCTION OF AMENDMENTS TO THE CONSTITUTION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IS AN ACTUAL ISSUE OF TODAY

Ziyadullaev Makhmudjon Djurakulovich

Professor of the University of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Head of the Department of Private and Legal Rights of the Specialized branch of Tashkent State Law University (PhD), Associate Professor

E-mail: maxmud1970@rambler.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6821144>

Introduction (Abstract): This article highlights the current issues of amendments to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the concepts, signs, functions of the social state and the legal basis for amendments to the Constitution.

The concepts of social protection, the history of origin and the reforms carried out in the field of social protection and proposals to the Constitution were developed.

Keywords: social state, social protection, social security, minimum pension expenses, retirement pension, old-age pension, preferential pension.

Indeed, The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on December 8, 1992, that is, in the first years of the country's independence. Over the past period, Uzbekistan, recognizing all the positive achievements achieved by world civilization, humanitarian values, international legal criteria and requirements, has been carrying out reforms in the field of social protection of the population in accordance with international standards. This activity manifests itself, first of all, in the creation of a legal basis for a new approach to human values, the introduction into the national system of positive provisions achieved in the course of human development.

As President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev noted on December 7, 2021 at a festive event dedicated to the 29th anniversary of the Constitution, "today's tense period requires us to take actions and changes appropriate to the time. I think that the preparation of a new draft of the basic law, its submission for public discussion and improvement on the basis of the proposals made, the adoption of this important political document during the celebration of the 30th anniversary of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022, in order to have a perfect Constitution that meets such requirements, will be a worthy work in the interests of our national statehood, in the interests of our the people".

It is known that the world's first constitution was adopted in the United States on September 17, 1787, and to date this Constitution has been amended 27 times. The Constitutions of the developed countries of the world, such as

Germany, France, Italy, Switzerland, have also been amended accordingly. Similarly, the CIS member states have repeatedly amended their constitutions. Almost all countries of the world as a whole make appropriate changes to their constitutions depending on socio-economic development. Each country decides for itself whether it should change the Constitution. Therefore, Uzbekistan has all the legal grounds to change its Constitution.

Many countries of the world define in their constitutions that they are a social state, including Article 7 of the Constitution of the Russian Federation states that "The Russian Federation is a social state and pursues a policy aimed at creating conditions that ensure a decent life and free human development," as well as article 1 of the Constitution of the Republic of Belarus states that it is also a welfare state, and Sweden, the People's Republic of China, the Scandinavian countries, similar concepts of the welfare state are reflected in the constitutions. The concept of the "welfare state" was first used by the German scientist Professor Lorenz von Stein of the University of Cologne in 1850. In the list of functions of the state, he included "the preservation of absolute equality in rights for various social classes, for a separate private self-determined person".

The state, according to Stein, is obliged to promote the economic and social progress of all its citizens, since, ultimately, the development of one is a condition for the development of the other, as he believed that the task of the state is to establish social equality and personal freedom, the elevation of the lower and disadvantaged classes to the level of the rich and powerful.

Signs of a welfare state (as a rule)

High level of economic development of the country,
which makes it possible to redistribute the income of the population without encroaching on large owners,
social market economy,
formation of civil society,
development of various social programs by the state,
approval of the goals of the state, providing everyone with decent living conditions,
equal starting conditions for social security and personal self-realization,
social responsibility to citizens,
ensuring their rights and freedoms., a developed system of contributions to social insurance and high level of taxes,
components of the budget, a high level of social contributions,

a developed system of services and social services for all groups of the population,
the separation of powers,
a developed legal system,
that clearly implements the functions of each branch of government,
a developed regulatory and legal system of social life,
the availability of budgetary social payments,
the availability of state social protection systems,
social security and employment for everyone without exception in need of social support for all members of society who are, there are signs such as the acceptance by the state of responsibility for the level of well-being of citizens, the presence of civil society institution.

Functions of the welfare State

Support for socially vulnerable segments of the population, the fight against unemployment, assistance to young entrepreneurs, ensuring employment growth and permanent incomes of the population, providing social insurance for all members of society, ensuring access to education, health care and spiritual and cultural development, social protection of the needy, mitigating social inequality in society, ensuring a decent life through the redistribution of benefits. creation of living conditions, provision of social services.

All these are elements that form the legal basis for defining it as a welfare state.

A social state is a model of a country whose policy is aimed at redistributing material goods in accordance with the principles of social justice in order to achieve a decent quality and standard of living for every citizen, mitigate social differences and provide assistance to those in need.

In a word, the welfare state means social guarantees. In our country, effective work is carried out in all of the above social areas.

In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to another aspect of the welfare State. Social guarantees exceed certain norms and should not contain any category of the population.

The work carried out in Uzbekistan on social protection issues.

Social protection – includes social security, financial assistance, housing, education, healthcare, employment issues and other social areas.

Since the country gained independence, special attention has been paid to social protection. Especially in the last 5-6 years, cardinal reforms have been carried out in all areas of social protection.

Including;

In the field of ensuring employment of the population - the creation of modern mono-centers for vocational training, providing a wide range of opportunities for public works, the introduction of subsidies to the poor;

Preschool education-almost until 2017 was in a deplorable state. Within the framework of the action strategy, the level of coverage of children with preschool education has been reached from 30 to 70 percent, private, family preschool educational institutions have been created;

in the field of general education-repair of schools, creation of specialized schools, presidential schools;

in the field of higher education - if until 2017 there were about 70 higher educational institutions in the republic, then by 2022 there are more than 160, especially foreign, private universities;

in the field of social security, problems with the payment of pensions have been eliminated, modern methods of assigning pensions have been introduced, electronic acceptance of applications has been introduced;

in the field of housing provision, rare successes have been achieved, in a very short period, more than 800 thousand houses have been built and put into operation;

Material provision -provision of financially secure segments of the population, especially during the pandemic, systematic provision of the population with material support, the establishment by introducing “Temir Daftar” of studying the social, economic, spiritual situation of each person and, based on this, the provision of appropriate practical assistance is assessed as a new module of Uzbekistan in international relations.

Without exaggeration, all this can be referred social reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan on the basis of the principle of human dignity.

In conclusion, the reforms carried out in the social sphere, the programs adopted, as well as in order to further strengthen the welfare of the people, human values and ensure the direct functioning of our laws, bringing them into line with international standards, have full legal grounds to call the new Uzbekistan a social state.

list of used literature:

1. <https://lex.uz/docs/20596>
2. <https://daryo.uz/k/2021/12/07/shavkat-mirziyoyev-ozbekiston-xalqini-8-dekabr-konstitutsiya-bayrami-bilan-tabrikladi>
3. Makhmudjon Djurakulovich Ziyadullaev. (2021). Development Of The Legislative System Of Non-State Pension Provision In The Republic Of

Uzbekistan . The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology, 3(03), 49–54. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajpslc/Volume03Issue03-08>

4. Djurakulovich, Ziyadullaev Makhmudjon. "Recognition in international documents of the right to social security as one of the most important human rights." Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research 10.10 (2021): 1372-1375.

5. Абдуллаева Д. Меҳнат шартномаси тушунчаси ва унинг турдош фуқаролик-ҳуқуқий шартномалардан фарқли жиҳатлари //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 9/S. – С. 317-327.

6. Abdullaeva D. LEGAL REGULATION OF PART-TIME WORK IN LABOR RELATIONS //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 04. – С. 5-12.

